

Methodische ansätze zur bewertung des niveaus der innovativen entwicklungsinfrastruktur in der region

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Abstrakt: Die entwicklung der Innovationstätigkeit in der region beinhaltet eine umfassende analyse der innovationstätigkeit, die eine verlässliche einschätzung des standes der innovationsentwicklung ermöglicht.

Schlüsselwörter: innovationstätigkeit, innovationen, wissenschaftliche forschung und experimentelle designarbeit, neue technologien, innovative infrastruktur, umwelt.

Methodological approaches to assessing the level of innovative development infrastructure in the region

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Abstract: The development of innovative activity in the region includes a comprehensive analysis of innovative activity, which allows for a reliable assessment of the level of innovative development.

Key words: innovative activity, innovations, scientific research and experimental design work, new technologies, innovative infrastructure, environment.

Introduction.

Innovative development of the country is impossible without stable economic growth of its regions. However, experience shows that there are disparities in the socio-economic development of regions. The basis for further development of the regions is the successful implementation of the regional innovation policy based on the innovation strategy of the region.

Analysis of literature.

One of the main conditions for the economic growth of the region is the growth of innovative activities of the public and private sectors of the economy.

However, currently there is no unanimity of opinion in the economic scientific literature on the methods of evaluating the level of innovative development of the region. Innovative activity is an independent category. With its help, the nature of innovative activity is evaluated. Scientists have different opinions on the selection of criteria and indicators for evaluating the innovative activity of regions. Thus, K.V. Podpyatnikova and I. P. Savelev defines innovative activity as "the purposeful activity

of regional business entities on the design, creation, development and production of high-quality equipment, labor products, intellectual property objects (patents, licenses, etc.), technologies, as well as labor organization and introducing more advanced forms of production management." A. Ter-Grigoryants and M. L. Ushvitsky recommend using indicators such as innovative activity of organizations to evaluate the innovative activity of the region; internal research and development costs per person engaged in scientific research and development ; the share of current practical research costs in the total costs; the share of advanced technologies used, the share of advanced technologies created; the share of post-graduate students with a thesis defense, and a number of other indicators [1]. In the work of P. Orekhovsky, it is proposed to characterize innovative activity according to the main indicators of the development of science and innovations used by the State Statistics Committee. Among the indicators characterizing innovative activity, the following are given: the number of personnel employed research and development; internal costs for research and development; costs for technological innovation; the number of Ph.D. theses defended; number of received patent applications and issuance of titles of protection; volume of innovative products by degree novelty; share of costs for technological innovations in the volume of shipped products innovation-active organizations [2].

The category "innovative activity of the region" should be considered as a real result of creation and introduction of innovations in production. Different levels of innovative activity in regions, calculated in specific quantities, allow to determine the state of innovative activity in the region and the level of efficiency of using available resources. The study of the level of innovative activity in the region can be carried out only on the basis of a set of interrelated private indicators and on the basis of combining them into a single integral indicator.

The research methodology consists of a set of methods of comparative, structural, functional and statistical analysis, a system approach, monographs survey, expert estimates, etc. In addition to quantitative analysis, a method of sociological surveys of participants of leasing relationships are used while the research.

Analysis and results.

All of the following indicators can be used as private indicators to evaluate the innovative activity of the region. In addition, all selected indicators meet the following requirements:

- Availability of indicators proposed in statistical reports of the state;
- uniformity of indicators, that is, the higher the value of the indicator, the higher the innovative activity of the region;
- the possibility of calculation based on selected indicators of private indices of innovative activity of the region;
- the ability to reduce private indices to a single value in order to determine the integral index of the innovative activity of the region.

At the initial stage of all three areas of research, research objects are determined based on its goals and scope. Next, the indicators presented in Table 1 are calculated based on the data collected on the development of innovative activities. In the first

direction of the methodology, complex indicators and an integral indicator of the level of efficiency of the development of innovative activities of the region are determined.

Table 1. Indicators of evaluation of the innovative development infrastructure of the region*

Indicators	Unit of measure	Signs
The share of innovative goods (works, services) in the total volume of GDP	%	$I_{ИМ}$
Expenditures on technological, marketing and organizational innovations in terms of innovative activities in the regions in relation to GNP	Billion sum	$I_{ММ}$
The ratio of the number of new technologies (technical achievements), software tools created by the regions of organizations engaged in scientific research and experimental design work	unity	I_1
The ratio of the number of new technologies (technical achievements), software tools created by region to 1000 employees engaged in scientific research and experimental design work	unity	I_2
The ratio of the number of patents to organizations engaged in scientific research and experimental construction work	unity	I_3
The ratio of the number of patents to the number of employees engaged in scientific research and experimental design work per 1000	unity	$I_{ИНМ}$
The ratio of the volume of innovative products, works, services produced by small enterprises and micro-firms to the total volume of innovative products, works, services	Billion sum	$I_{ТДМ}$

* Compiled by the author

Based on the selected private indicators, private indices were calculated for each indicator to compare their levels by region. The calculation of private indices was carried out using econometric models for the period from 2016 to 2020. The minimum and maximum values for each of the private indices were determined. Private indices are calculated using the following formulas (Table 2)

Table 2. Calculation indices of the innovative development infrastructure of the region*

$I_{ИМ}$ –innovative production environment	$I_{ИМ} = \sqrt[2]{\frac{И_T}{ЯХМ}}$
$I_{ММ}$ –financial environment	$I_{ММ} = \sqrt[2]{\frac{Х}{ЯХМ}}$
$I_{ТМ}$ –technological environment	$I_{ТМ} = I_1 + I_2 + I_3$
	$I_1 = \sqrt[2]{\frac{Т}{Т_{ИТТКИ}}}$
	$I_2 = \sqrt[2]{\frac{Т}{Х_{ИТТКИ}}}$
	$I_3 = \sqrt[2]{\frac{П}{Т_{ИТТКИ}}}$
$I_{ИММ}$ –Intellectual environment	$I_{ИММ} = \sqrt[2]{\frac{П}{Х_{ИТТКИ}}}$
$I_{ТДМ}$ –Business environment	$I_{ТДМ} = \sqrt{\frac{К_{МХ}}{И_{ту}}}$

* Compiled by the author

There are functional links between the private indices and the integrated index of the innovative activity of the region. In order to comprehensively assess the innovative activity of the region, we suggest using the integrated index defined as the fifth root of the results of the five indices:

$$I_{ИФ} = \sqrt[5]{I_{ИМ} * I_{ММ} * I_{ТМ} * I_{ИММ} * I_{ТДМ}},$$

$I_{ИФ}$ – integrated index of innovative activity of the region.

Index weight coefficients of each subsystem of regional innovative development institutions are equal to 1, which ensures equal consideration of the impact of each component. Based on the results of calculating the complex and integral index, the regions are divided according to the level of development of regional innovative development institutions for innovative activities presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Determining the level of development of the innovative infrastructure of the region by the value of complex indicators*

№ group	Indicator value	The level of innovative development of the region
1	0,8-1	High
2	0,6-0,8	Enough
3	0,4-0,6	Medium

4	0,2-0,4	Weak
5	0-0,2	Low

* Compiled by the author

In order to determine the dynamics of development of subsystems and innovative activities of the region, the average annual growth rates of the indicators are calculated and compared with the general level in the country.

Testing of the methodology was carried out by the Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan based on statistical data describing the development of the period from 2016 to 2020.

Conclusion. Thus, the proposed methodology for evaluating the level of innovative activity allows to diagnose the state of the innovation system of the region and quantitatively assess the productivity of innovative activity. For innovative development, it is necessary to create the necessary conditions for successfully managing innovative processes, increasing the efficiency of innovative activities and increasing the competitiveness of regions.

References:

1. Ter-Grigoryants A. A. Methodological approaches to assessing the innovative development of the region // Region. economics: theory and practice. - 2013. - No. 10. - p. 49–56.
2. Orekhovsky P. Evaluation of the effectiveness of innovations in the regions: a comparative analysis // Society and Economics. - 2007. - No. 5-6. - With. 203-215.